

Evaluation of mechanical properties for CFRTP using *in situ*-polymerizing thermoplastic urethane resin

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Background and Objective

CFRTP (Carbon Fiber Reinforced ThermoPlastics)

CFRTP have several excellent characteristics.

Melt viscosity of thermoplastic resin is very high.

New Development

CFRTP using *in situ*-polymerizing thermoplastic urethane resin

- Very low viscosity before curing.
- Polymerizes linearly after impregnation.

Laminate fibers and impregnate resin

Push out excess resin

Heat and press

Constitute materials

Type of test specimen	Type of resin	Type of fiber
PU-CFRTP	Thermoplastic urethane resin H-6FP17 (DKS)	Twill woven carbon fiber fabric W-3161 (TEIJIN)
EP-CFRTP	Thermoplastic epoxy resin XNR6850A (Nagase ChemteX corporation)	
AC-CFRTP	Thermoplastic acrylic resin Elium 190 (ARKEMA)	
CFRP	Thermosetting epoxy resin XNR6805 (Nagase ChemteX corporation)	

※ Fiber volume content of all specimens are about 60 %.

PU-CFRTP can be molded by the same method as the ordinary CFRP.

Objective : Evaluate the mechanical properties of PU-CFRTP.

Experiments and Results

Three-point bending tests.

Bending properties of PU-CFRTP are equivalent to other specimens.

Dynamic viscoelastic measurement

Loss tangent of PU-CFRTP shows the maximum value at about 160°C.

PU-CFRTP has higher Tg than others.

Bending test at elevated temperatures

PU-CFRTP shows less decline in bending strength and failure strain.

Creep test (At 80°C, 30% of bending strength)

PU-CFRTP is difficult to creep.

— PU-CFRTP — EP-CFRTP - - AC-CFRTP - · - CFRP

Conclusions

CFRTP using *in situ*-polymerizing thermoplastic urethane resin

- Excellent bending properties
- High heat and creep resistance